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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ «ТЕРМИНАТОР» В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ТЕМЫ «МИКРОПРОЦЕССОРНАЯ РЕЛЕЙНАЯ ЗАЩИТА»

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Аннотация. В статье описана методика использования нового интерактивного метода при преподавании темы микропроцессорной защиты по предмету «Релейная защита и автоматика» в высших технических учебных заведениях. Показана важность использования новых педагогических технологий для студентов, обучающихся по инженерному направлению, и его особенности. В нем подчеркивается важность внедрения новых педагогических технологий для студентов инженерных специальностей и излагаются его определяющие характеристики. Представлено разъяснение разработанного метода «Терминатор» среди студентов и результаты экспериментальных исследований, проведенных среди них. В ходе лекционной сессии были выявлены факторы, которые приводят к повышению показателей мастерства. Также было проанализировано влияние психических и социальных причин на углубление знаний студентов.

Ключевые слова: техника, инженер, обучение, освоение, интерактивный метод, педагогическая технология, микропроцессор, полупроводник.

THE USE OF INTERACTIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY “TERMINATOR” IN THE TEACHING OF THE SUBJECT OF MICROPROCESSOR RELAY PROTECTION

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Annotation. In the article, the method of using a new interactive method in the teaching of the topic of microprocessor protection on the subject of "Relay protection and automation" in higher technical educational institutions was described. The importance of using new pedagogical technologies for students studying in the field of engineering and its features were shown. It highlights the significance of incorporating new pedagogical technologies for students in engineering fields and outlines its defining characteristics. Explanation of the developed "Terminator" method among students and the results of experimental research conducted among them were presented. During the lecture session, the factors that lead to the increase of mastery indicators were identified. Also, the influence of mental and social reasons in deepening students' knowledge was analysed.

Keywords: technique, engineer, training, acquisition, interactive method, pedagogical technology, microprocessor, semiconductor.

Introduction. Commenting on the relevance of the research to be carried out based on the issues of teaching at the level of technical higher educational institutions, it is worth mentioning that even though a lot of work has been done in the field of education, there are several problems in the effective implementation of teaching [1, 2, 3].

Until now, methodological, scientific and psychological approaches to teaching have been carried out mainly by researchers educated in higher educational institutions of pedagogy, and several useful recommendations and guidelines have been put into practice [4, 5, 6].

However, precisely because the amount of such important work is not at a satisfactory level, raising the level of knowledge of students in technical higher educational institutions, professional educational institutions, and technical institutes is among the problems [7, 8].

It is not a secret that in many countries graduates of technical higher education institutions do not work in their fields, but on the contrary, despite having a diploma, remain unemployed, or work in a completely different field, sometimes as a "black worker" because they do not have deep knowledge, and "forcefully" graduate from universities. An expert can only be competitive with his strong knowledge. The rapid development of science and technology, the ability to keep up with industry experts, that is, the ability to quickly master new technology, use it competently, correct some malfunctions, modernize them and create new designs. To meet such requirements, it is necessary to develop during the student period the most necessary creativity, resourcefulness and understanding. It is very important and necessary for pedagogues of technical educational institutions to fulfil such skilful teaching characteristics. It is known that a teacher can teach a learner only when he/she has deep knowledge. In addition, it is desirable if they not only know different methods and ways of teaching but also can develop new methods. Because here, the large number of students in the audience, and the presence of various individuals who may be in different mental states, it is necessary to invent new methods, apply them on a large scale, and study their results to make their mastery of science as high as possible [9,10]. True, it must be recognized that there are good scientific articles in some foreign and domestic pedagogic journals. But firstly, they are published in different languages, so it is not possible to know all foreign languages at the same time, secondly, these publications rarely reach the hands of pedagogues all over the planet, and thirdly, all possibilities have not been considered yet. The works of pedagogic scientists in the field of humanities are intended for professors and teachers of pedagogical educational institutions. They do not know the intricacies of teaching technical subjects. But qualified and experienced teachers, who have worked for many years in higher technical and vocational educational institutions, and have also been involved in production activities for a certain period, have methods that cannot be popularized. It is for this reason that one area of research work should be devoted to the methodology and methodology of teaching technical sciences.

Problem statement. It is known that twenty-first-century techniques and technology are based on integrated circuits, microprocessor technology,

nanotechnology and electronics. At the bottom of these fields lies a complex of tools and equipment consisting of equipment made of materials with semiconducting properties.

Looking at the other side of the issue, to properly and efficiently operate such structures, it is necessary to have a good understanding of the physical, chemical and mechanical processes that take place inside the devices in order to increase their service life. A specialist who cannot imagine such processes will undoubtedly face several problems in working with the device, and at worst will not be able to do it. An engineer or a worker with such knowledge cannot be expected to offer rationalization proposals or initiate creative works. As a result, production growth is lost.

Based on the above observations, professors and specialists with technical education working in higher educational institutions, while teaching this or that subject, deeply mastering the physical and chemical processes that take place in the volume of equipment, moreover, do not use formulas as empty numbers, but "infuse them with life" explanation should be expected to be taught. There is another important issue for students in the process of studying at technical schools. It is a matter of being able to distinguish, read, and more precisely "talk" with technical drawings, schemes, conditional designations, and graphs [11,12]. This problem is the same as learning a foreign language. In learning a foreign language it is important to memorize vocabulary and be able to use them in their place, in learning the technical field it is so important to be able to understand conventional signs and units of measurement in drawings and graphs. If the experts have enough knowledge, they can distinguish what information is available by looking at graphs and charts. They use it and use it where they need it. It is known from our many years of pedagogical activity that most students feel bored when they see drawings, graphs and formulas. They don't want to read and learn because they don't understand them. New pedagogical technologies to be developed will have to take these issues into account.

A lack of understanding alone is not the cause of student barriers to reading and learning. Since the students grew up in families of different social origin, there are some age differences, the fact that they did not enter the university immediately after graduating from school, the presence of gap years in between, the fact that they are married and their parents are not present, that they live without or in the absence of financial deficiencies, the things that happen in life the presence of family issues and problems also has a negative effect on the level of mastery [4,13].

Here, it is necessary to be literate from a psychological point of view, precisely from the teacher of technical science. The great pedagogue Makarenko did not state the conclusion that "a teacher is an engineer of a person's soul" for nothing.

Therefore, based on the above problems, it is recommended to use methods that can be interesting for all listeners or easy to understand, taking into account both scientific and spiritual aspects of the teaching process. Game-based methods proposed by other scientists for this are commendable [15].

However, in addition to it, it is possible to use the events and phenomena of everyday life, objects, and events that occur in the natural environment. It is appropriate to use the theory of similarity in the implementation of this task [12,14].

The presented article, as a confirmation of our opinion, describes the methodology of teaching using the recommended interactive method of explaining microprocessor equipment from modern equipment made of semiconductor materials to students of a technical higher education institution. This interactive method was developed by the author and was practically applied and tested among the students of the power engineering faculty of the Polytechnic Institute.

Interactive method theory. Microprocessor devices are at the core of twenty-first-century technology. Currently, a significant part of energy and automatic equipment is implemented based on microprocessor control. Issues of quality control, transmission, distribution, and protection against accidents are studied in the subject "Relay protection and automation of the power supply system" conducted in the field of specialization. However, undergraduate electrical engineering and electrical engineering students rarely study electronics or semiconductor physics in an in-depth, multi-hour course. In this direction, a lot of attention is paid to the production of energy, working principles of substations, equipment, electric machines, etc., and they face great difficulties and problems when it comes to the use and operation of new types of protective equipment.

There is another reason for this: when the science of relay protection is taught, more attention is paid to the types of protection than to the protection equipment. These reasons lead to certain obstacles for power engineers when using protection devices, especially equipment consisting of microprocessor devices. Because integrated microcircuits with a microprocessor consist of a complex of diodes, thyristors, stabilizations, transistors, etc., made of almost

semiconductor materials (Figures 1 and 2), the physical processes occurring inside them are not understood.

Figure 1. The composition of integrated circuit blocks

Figure 2. Protection and control microprocessor view

An engineer who can correctly interpret such physical processes, in addition to being able to use protection, can repair equipment in case of damage, change its composition, modernize, and even find scientific solutions. Therefore, despite the short hours allocated, the possibility of effective teaching must be available to the science teacher. Physical processes in the volume of semiconductor materials occur due to the movement of electrons. But these actions are diverse and decisive, and to understand them, it is best to guide the student's mind through the imagination. As for imagination, great opportunities can be gained through similes. In this regard, with the participation of the author of this article, several suggestions and recommendations were given in open publications [11,12].

An interactive method called "Terminator" is now recommended to visualize the working principles and operation of a complete microprocessor. The reason why this interactive method is called "Terminator" is because the audience of school age almost all remember the movie that was shown on the cinema screens. In addition, they also know that a cybernetic machine in the form of a terminator can think in addition to fully performing actions that a human can perform. During the film, the breakdowns and fractures of the terminator body show that there is a complex consisting of various devices (integrated microcircuits) in its volume. When explaining the principles of operation of these devices and what tasks they can perform, the science teacher explains to the

students that every single movement of the terminator is performed based on the program, and the ability to think is also implemented through such programming through the semiconductor and other types of devices using the example of the terminator. For example, sensing the approaching danger through sensors, the arm and wrist of the robot terminator prepare to strike, and when the danger approaches a certain distance, it strikes back. This situation can be explained in the science of relay protection, that in the environment of protection against short circuit currents that may occur in power lines, the microprocessor protection device is implemented by exchanging data with other types of blocks of the tasking and executive bodies. The danger in the case of the terminator is that the short-circuit current in the relay protection exceeds the specified value, or the voltage changes by more than the permissible percentage, etc. Sensors installed in the eyes of the terminator act as a sensing organ (Fig. 3).

The science teacher explains that light, heat, electricity and other types of sensors must be used, depending on the physical magnitude of the danger. It is explained that mechanical actions such as walking, running, bending, and bending in the terminator are performed by executive bodies, in relay protection, or through mechanical relays or semi-conductor relays based on integrated circuits (Fig. 4). Here, it is appropriate to explain the principles of operation of diodes with one-way conduction characteristics, based on the theory of zones [12]. That is, if the amount of energy given to the electrons is sufficient, they can go through the p- and n-transition and generate an electric current, and if the amount of this electric current is sufficient, the executive body will act, otherwise, the task will not be performed.

Figure 3. Terminator and the location of the sensors that act as the organ of vision

Figure 4. A view of the structure of the moving mechanism in the arm of the Terminator

The independent automatic operation of the terminator can be represented by the structural diagram shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 5. A structural diagram of the automation of a certain operation (walking, running, one of the movements of the arms and legs and other parts of the body)

In the diagram shown in Figure 5, X is the command signal, Y is the controlled parameter, and this is the mechanical movement in the terminator, 1st sensor, 2nd switching device, 3rd amplifying device, 4th execution mechanism. The assignment is given through the program. The assignment for the terminator can be a body or a predefined object, the magnitude of the dangerous physical parameter in relay protection. If the initial signal in the terminator is a danger in the form of a body or object coming from the opposite side, a dangerous value of current or voltage in relay protection (for example, short-circuit current). The function of converter 2 and amplifier 3 is to convert the signal coming from the sensors, i.e. the physical quantity into a physical quantity that can be sensed by the next elements of the automatic control system, and it is necessary to amplify it in terms of power. Because not all mechanisms perceive the same physical magnitude. For example, a drive motor uses electrical currents to make muscles stretch and contract. However, at the same time, thermal energy and radiation can be transmitted from the primary receiving element-heat sensor and not received by the electromotive.

In the process of explaining this method, it is explained how the automatic work performed is done with the help of electricity or other equipment. Their structural structures and principles of operation are described.

Analysis of the procedure and results of experimental research. Since the implementation of this interactive method was designed to attract the attention of students in the entire audience, the first experimental research was conducted during lectures on "Relay Protection and Automation" among undergraduate students of the Faculty of Energy of Fergana Polytechnic Institute in the field of "Electric Power" and master's degree in "Power Supply" 54 undergraduate students participated in the first stage of the experiment. It was a one-stream audience consisting of two groups, and the topic "Maximum Current Protection

of Power Lines" was initially chosen. The topic was explained using the technical terms used traditionally without talking about the recommended interactive method. Then, after the appropriate question-and-answer procedure, it was asked who could speak on the topic. Hesitation and hesitance were evident among the students. After some time, only one student expressed his desire to express his understanding of the topic.

In the course of the student's speech, I did not remember technical terms but used words that are more similar but also have different meanings. On the topic, he could not answer the question of how the defence could work when conflicting situations arise. Then the audience was asked for help and additional ideas. Another student expressed his opinion, but some misconceptions raised by the students were corrected by the science teacher. The analysis of the result revealed that a large percentage of the students in the audience were sitting as spectators rather than being active.

In the second stage of the experiment, the recommended interactive "Terminator" method was used and the subject was explained. At first, when the students were reminded of the film of the same name, and when they were asked who had seen it and what its content was, the audience felt a sense of revitalization.

Instead of waiting in line, the students began to speak their thoughts and ideas. At some moments, when there was agreement between the opinions, negotiations and mutual explanations-discussions began. The science teacher, in order not to lose time, explained that the main character's activity in this particular film is a product of an automatic system and that all his work is a product of a schematic complex of interconnected technical equipment, equipment with semiconductor properties.

Then, to check the students' knowledge, write a written statement about what physical process occurs when an overload phenomenon occurs on power lines, the reasons for this process, compare these processes with similar phenomena and situations encountered in everyday life, or what they can give examples of situations in other similar films. control case received. The first reason for conducting the control work in a written form was that all the students were eager to answer at the same time, and it was not possible to listen to all of their wishes during the hour allocated for the lecture, moreover, the pedagogue did not have time to correct and interpret possible mistakes. The second reason was the need to understand what the students wanted to say when they wrote down their thoughts clearly and clearly and to evaluate each one's work.

The graph of the results obtained as a result of the experiments is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Histogram representation of the results of experimental studies conducted among undergraduate and graduate students.

It is clear from the obtained results that the interactive method gave a positive result. That is, among graduate and undergraduate students, the achievement of "excellent" comprehension and mastery tasks (line 1 indicators) increased. At the same time, the number of "good" (line 2) and "satisfactory" (line 3) jobs also increased. The number of students who did not master (4th yellow line) decreased. In both groups, only one student failed to learn, and when they were investigated why such a result was achieved, it was found that one did not participate in the lesson, and the other was neglected because he was ill. During the examination of the control work, the science teacher paid special attention to the student's creative approach. During each lecture, the student's explanation of the unspoken thoughts and opinions with other examples was also positively evaluated. However, their shortcomings and mistakes were also pointed out here.

Conclusions. As a result of the application of the developed interactive method and its practical experimental testing, it was found that, although they are complex subjects, they can be achieved with the help of various methods to

improve the student audience's understanding of technical subjects and their mastery, and this is often positive, will undoubtedly give results. The most important of the conducted practical activities is to create a live situation in the audience and to focus maximum attention on the topics related to the topic. Such an approach teaches the student studying the topic to think over several similar examples to compare them and draw conclusions. The indicated mistakes and shortcomings serve to strengthen the level of knowledge. Thinking through visualizations also helps students to identify their own mistakes in some cases. This is necessarily done by finding the difference between an object or phenomenon that simulates some physical process.

References.

1. Беспалько, В.П. Педагогика и прогрессивные технологии обучения. М.: Педагогическое сообщество России, 2003. 322 с.
2. Бордовская, Н.В., Реан А.А. Педагогика. М.: Питер, 2015. 299 с. ISSN 2412-8201.
3. Ryabokony E. A., Krecan Z. V., Shmakova L. E. Visualization of Educational Information as a Means of Enhancing the Cognitive Activity in Students // Bulletin of Kemerovo State University. Series: Humanities and Social Sciences. 2020. no. 2. pp. 126-136. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21603/2542-1840-2020-4-2-126-136> (Date of access 08.09.2023).
4. Шадрин Н. С. Психология личности // Астана: Фолиант. – 2012.
Немов, Р.С. Психология. Учебник. Книга 1 / Р.С. Немов. – М.: Владос, 2003. – 688 с.
5. Гусейнов, Э.А. Исследование личности студента в процессе обучения / Э.А. Гусейнов // Актуальные проблемы психологии, педагогики и общественных наук, выпуск 1, часть 1. – М.: РГСУ, 2006. – С. 223–226.
6. Platonova, D.P. Universities at a Crossroads: Higher Education in Russia / Series of Collective Monographs / Edited by D.P. Platonova, Ya. I. Kuzminova, I. D. Frumina. Higher School of Economics Publishing House. – Moscow. – 2019.
7. Бородич, С.А. Балльно-рейтинговая система оценки знаний студентов в вузе: проблемы и перспективы / С.А. Бородич, А.Н. Тепляковская // Инновационные педагогические технологии: материалы IV Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Казань, май 2016 г.). – Казань: Бук, 2016. – С. 139-141.
8. Башевой, С.И. Применение методов активного обучения в форме «Лекция вдвоем» в преподавании ряда дисциплин / С.И. Башевой, Э.И. Кузнецова // Вестник ассоциации вузов туризма и сервиса. – 2012. – № 2. – С. 58-63.
9. Киличева Ф., Дэниелс Г., Саипова М., Якубова Ш., Кошназарова М. Передовые технологии развития критического мышления при формировании информационно-познавательной активности студентов.

- ISSN 2412-8201. Pedagogy & Psychology. Theory and practice. 2022. № 2 (40).
10. Kasimaxunova A.M., Atajonova S.B. Use of innovative learning methods in the classes on the subject: "theory of automatic control. Scientific-technical journal (STJ FerPI, ФарПИ ИТЖ, НТЖ ФерПИ, 2021, Т.25, спец. №1). pp.147-151.
 11. Касимахунова А.М. Шаходжаев М.А. Методика обучения студентов по зонной теории применения метода «армия электронов». Бюллетень науки и практики / Bulletin of Science and Practice <https://www.bulletennauki.com>. Т. 7. №9. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/70>. Стр. 535-541.
 12. Шадрин, Н.С. Система категорий психологии и понятия индивида, субъекта деятельности и личности: некоторые уроки концепций Канта, Фихте, Гегеля и Сартра / Н.С. Шадрин // Вестник ОмГУ. Серия Психология. – 2020. – № 1 – С. 24–36.
 13. Зуев К.И. Теория подобия. Министерство образования и науки Российской Федерации Государственное образовательное учреждение высшего профессионального образования «Владимирский государственный университет имени А. Г. и Н. Г. Столетовых». Владимир 2011.
 14. Василенко, В.Г. Игровые методы проведения учебных занятий в высшей школе / В.Г. Василенко // Вестник РМАТ. – 2014. – № 1 (10). – С. 84-94.

ОГЛАВЛЕНИЕ

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ В ЦИФРОВОМ– ДИСТАНЦИОННОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ.

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